

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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Prevalence of injuries in preschool children and their specific medical and social importance in prevention.

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Annotation. In the article, the results of scientific studies devoted on the distribution of injuries among children, especially in children of preschool age, or more specifically, injuries in life, and the medical and social aspects of the factors to be affected it, are analyzed. Marital injuries among children of preschool age remain today as one of the most important medical and social problems in all countries of the world, included in our country, especially in Khorezm region, where our research is planned, and in some cases it is increasing.

According to JCCT data, more than 850,000 children under the age of 18 die each year due to various injuries, poisoning and other effects of the external environment. Thousands of children are left with life long disabilities as a result of their injuries. Although the main causes of injuries in children of preschool age are similar to in most countries, they also have peculiarities related to certain lifestyles, and in many cases parents do not take into account the interests of children, especially 1-3-year-old children, and it occurs as a result of negligence.

Key words: Children, preschool children, family injury, prevalence, medical and social disability, deats.

Relevance of the topic

All over the world, injuries and violence among children, especially preschool children, remain one of the leading causes of death among them. According to the World Health Organization, more than 850,000 children under the age of 18 die each year due to various injuries, poisonings and other effects of the external environment. Thousands of children are disabled for life as a result of their injuries. The main part of it is motor transport accidents and drownings. In the last 15 years, the Russian Federation has a high rate of death due to accidents in children, and it is 20.0-29.9 tenge per 100,000 children, which is 3-4 times higher than the Scandinavian countries (5.0-9.9/100). per thousand children) [1]. Am. horses are formed. It is noteworthy that during the studied years, injuries in marriage showed an increase (from 2003 -24.9% to 2007 -31.%). Especially among 0-14-year-olds,

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during games (26.7%) and cases of falling from above (38.9%) were observed at a high level. by V. M. Krestyashin (2003) [3]

according to the scientific conclusions, the number of injuries in marriage in children is in the first place, making up 70% of all injuries. The author's grief in his life, the new house that comes from this house, and the wounds he received on the stairs are listed. When going to school, this is a degree program. Burns account for 20% of injuries, especially in infants. However, in many literatures, all types of children's injuries are included in family injuries. Depending on the outcome of the accident, it is learned in the process of childbirth, marriage, school, sports, strength, severe burns, drowning, falling from a height and others. The author concluded that one of the most vital ways to reduce domestic violence among pre-school children is to prevent life-threatening injuries to their parents and prevent them from harming their children. The main basis of the research is the distribution of injuries in life among preschool children and its main reasons on the work and analysis of the report published by the ad statistician.

Materials and methods

In the world, in the last few years, in the past few years, there have been studies of statistics and scientific researches, which have been studied from the literature, and the studies that have been carried out among the children of private schools are complex in all aspects. analytical and photographic research methods.

Results and discussion

Although the main causes of injuries in children of preschool old age are similar in most countries, they also have specific characteristics related to certain lifestyles and in many cases are caused by parents' neglect and neglect of the interests of children, especially children aged 1-3 years. According to a report presented by **whom** and UNICEF, 830,000 children die prematurely due to injuries worldwide.

Tens of millions of children are disabled due to injuries. Every year, more than 600,000 people are injured in Kazakhstan, and 20% of them are children. It is noted that these are mainly caused by falls from above, burns and motor vehicle accidents. Injuries in boys are 2-3 times higher. The author suggests implementing preventive measures aimed at reducing injuries in children in three directions, i.e. individual, group and collective [4,6]. O. V. Golovko, T. N. Pavlenko and others. (2017) [5] study results show that children aged 0-3 years - 40% of acute poisonings, preschoolers - 12.4%, 7-15 years - 25.9% and It was determined that 15-17-year-

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olds accounted for -21.7%. Including medical drugs - with 51.8%, the first place, poisoning with chemical substances in life - the second - with 18.5%, alcoholic beverages and its substitutes - the third with 16.2%, and 13.5% were various poisonings. It is the worth thing that 45.5% of those who received thermal burns corresponded to children of early age, one out of three burns were children under one year of age. These presented data show that all types of injuries are relatively high in preschool children and require a deep scientific analysis of its medical and social aspects. A significant number of injuries among preschool children are caused by burns for various reasons. In the Russian Federation, more than 300,000 people die each year due to burns, and 100,000 people become disabled. One in six fires are caused by children's careless actions. It is emphasized that the main task of parents in the prevention of such injuries is to explain to children in detail the meaning and essence of the activity "it can't be done" and why it is impossible, in the form of a miniature version of adult fire fighting activities, in the form of a game. [6]. According to WHO, 6% of all injuries in the world are thermal burns, and this situation is increasing every year. Children account for 20% of burn deaths. 61% of burn injuries occur in men and 19% in women. 85% of burns in children were registered in preschool and 15% in school-aged children, 54% of them were children aged 1-3 years. 69.6% of burns occurred in urban and 30.4% rural children. It is noteworthy that 93% of burns in children were thermal, 2% were caused by chemical substances, and 5% were various other burns[7,8]. T.N. Pavlenko, O.V. Golovko's (2015) [9] research results show that burns are the second leading cause of death among children, and in Russia, this rate is 1.2% in inpatients. Analysis showed that 45.5% of burns are due to children of early age registered and one out of every three cases involved children under 1 year old (10.1%), 18.6% -3-7 years old, 22.4% -7-14 years old and 13.4% -12-18 years old In fact, 67% of those hospitalized were boys and 33% were girls, and it can be seen that the number of burns in boys is twice as high. 54% of burns are caused by boiling water, 25.1% by fire, 11.8% by hot objects, 6.5% by electric shock, 2.0% by steam, and 0.5% by various chemicals. it was determined that it occurred. Most of the injuries that occur in school-aged children are associated with eye injuries and are characterized by severe complications. The results of the scientific research conducted in Tajikistan show that in 2009, 27.9% of injuries occurred in children, in 2010 - 27.3%, and the most eye injuries were among children aged 3-6 years and boys in villages [10, 11].

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According to the results of studies carried out in the Perm region of Russia, in 2014 and 2015, a total of 39,801 people presented with eye injuries, and 4,078 of them (10.2%) were children. 41 of them aged 1-17 were admitted to the hospital. 30 of them (73%) were boys and 11 (27%) were girls. 23 of the victims were injured in their homes, 17 in the street, and 1 in the school. Notably, 43 eye injuries were reported in 41 injured children, 31 had lacerations (72%), 8 (19%) had contusions, and 4 (9%) had burns [12]. The conclusions of G.Z. Galeeva et al. (2017) [13] show that eye injuries in children make up 9-10% of all injuries in child old age. According to the authors, trauma in children has a youthful nature, and it is said that leadership is important in preschool children aged 4-7 years. It is noted that more eye injuries are received by people older than 2 years (23%), 3-4 years -17%, 5-6 years -15%, 7-8 years -13%, 9-11 and 12-16 years -16% organized. In addition to that more eye injuries were observed in the hot months of the year (38.3%), especially among urban children. Electrocutions are relatively rare in children, but they are of particular importance due to their complications, namely the significantly higher mortality and disability rates. Rubtsov V.V., Tsap N.A. and others. (2016) [14] in the years 2010-2015 in Yekaterinburg, Sverdlovsk region. When studying a total of 51 electrocuted patients who were treated in the children's burn center No. 9, it was found that 39 of them were boys and 12 were girls, more than half of the studied (24) were children under 3 years old, 10 were teenagers aged 13-15, 9 were of junior school age. and it is noted that 8 of them were children aged 4-7.

It is the worthy thing that in the epidemiology of electric injuries, 76% of those who suffered (39) received electric injuries as a result of direct contact with electrical equipment in living conditions, while 12 (24%) received electric injuries in high-voltage networks. In both cases, the children received electrical injuries due to the negligence of their parents. 83% of the injured were from the city of Ekaterinburg, and the rest were children living in rural areas. Another type of injury in children before school age is congenital hip dislocation in newborn babies. According to the results of the scientific studies carried out in the Samarkand branch of the Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 1988, a total of 310 children applied to the center due to registered diseases, 39 of them (35.2%) were left-sided, 55 (49.5%)) was right-sided and 17 (15.3%) had bilateral femur protrusion. 17.1% of them were treated by surgery. According to some data, in 48.7% of cases, such congenital injuries are detected when the child

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begins to walk [15,16]. R.N.Akalaev, G.N.Sukhodolova and others. (2018) [17], 1.5 million children and adolescents are poisoned every year in the USA, and it is said that this constitutes 67% of the total poisonings. According to the direct research conducted by the authors, in 2011-2015, a total of 6,789 children were admitted to the toxicology department of the Children's Clinical Hospital No. 13 named after N.A. Filatov in Moscow, and 1,786 poisoned children were admitted to the toxicology department of the Republican Emergency Medical Center studies show a high rate of poisoning from toxic substances in various living conditions among children, especially children of preschool age. It is noteworthy that 63.6% of those poisoned were children under the age of 7, the saddest thing is that this process is increasing year by year, one of the main causes for this is the poisons used in the family's living conditions, improper storage of medicines and neglect of parents. is counted.

Conclusions

1. From the scientific conclusions to be continued in the literature studied and analyzed above, it became clear that in recent years in many countries of the world, including our country, the percentage of injuries among children, especially children of preschool age, especially injuries in marriage, is large and growing.

2. Scientific research on the medical and social aspects of the prevalence of domestic injuries in children, especially among children of preschool age, was carried out in most cases abroad, in particular in individual regions and large cities of the Russian Federation, as well as in the CIS countries. In our country, especially in the case of Khorezm region, where we are planning to carry out scientific research, there has been no study of marital injuries among children of preschool age.

3. The analysis showed that most of the injuries among preschool children occur at home, on the street, in kindergartens, on sports fields, as a result of neglect of children by parents and educators, due to their negligence. At the same time, it was found that children are not given sufficient knowledge, qualifications and skills on safety rules from an early age in the family and educational institutions.

4. Based on the study and analysis of the literature focused on the causes of marital injuries and their spread among preschool children, the conclusion is that in our country, moreover, based on the materials of the Khorezm region, which differs from other regions with some specific characteristics, this process requires a scientific study of this process from a complex socio-hygienic point of view.

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